

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Report on workflow pitfalls

Deliverable 12

Work Package 4

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Executive summary

Environmental DNA (eDNA) workflows are increasingly important for aquatic biodiversity monitoring, but the steps from sampling and sequencing to analysis and publication remain fragmented and difficult to align with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. The EU project eDNAqua-Plan seeks to address this by developing a digital landscape (proposed by Work Package 3) and testing its operational feasibility across the eDNA workflow through the combined expertise of freshwater and marine use cases (Work Package 4). To this end, WP4 focused on 1) developing effective DMPs for aquatic eDNA studies, 2) streamlining the submission of sequence data to ENA as European INSDC repository, 3) enhancing interoperability across different data components of eDNA projects, 4) making laboratory protocols and 5) bioinformatic workflows FAIR, 6) evaluating eDNA data uploads to global biodiversity portals and 7) aiming for reliable taxonomic assignment of sequence data in eDNA studies. The objective of this deliverable is to identify strengths and challenges of the current digital landscape and to provide specific recommendations to make eDNA data flows more efficient, interoperable and FAIR-compliant.

The use cases found that current Data Management Plan (DMP) platforms have generic templates, leaving uncertainty about which datasets need to be added, which metadata need to be provided, and which standards need to be used to have a meaningful DMP. Submitting sequence data to ENA (as the central European INSDC eDNA repository) was identified by use cases to be impractical and insufficiently automated, while interoperability across platforms is hampered by misalignment between the recommended FAIR checklist and ENA (and also NCBI) templates. The structured BeBOP laboratory protocols offer valuable templates for PCR-based protocols that can be tailored to study specific workflows. The metagenomic template is, however, insufficient to properly describe a metagenomics workflow. Similarly, bioinformatic workflows for eDNA metabarcoding datasets are well covered by existing metadata standards, while key processes in metagenomics such as assembly, binning, and annotation are currently poorly documented in the FAIR checklist. Uploads to biodiversity portals like GBIF and OBIS are facilitated by the Metabarcoding Toolkit, which is a well documented and easy process. Finally, a continuous central challenge in eDNA studies is assigning a robust taxonomic name to eDNA sequences. Even when all metadata of a reference sequence are provided, this does not guarantee a correct taxonomic identification of the specimen from which the sequence was derived.

Based on these challenges, WP4 recommends developing eDNA-specific DMP templates that integrate existing standards such as MIxS, DwC, and FAIR. ENA submissions should be simplified with better integration of FAIR metadata and short, user-friendly guidelines. Interoperability across repositories should be strengthened by developing conversion scripts to align FAIR fields with repository templates. To make laboratory protocols FAIR, more accessible controlled vocabularies are needed. The FAIR checklist, BeBOP laboratory protocols and biodiversity portals should integrate metagenomic extensions to make the digital landscape ready for the future. Finally, reliable taxonomic assignment requires curated reference databases and bioinformatic scripts with quality control steps to minimise wrong taxonomic assignments.

In all, even small steps can make a big difference in lowering barriers for users, ensuring that the digital landscape is truly adopted. Therefore, materials that increase the operational aspect of the digital landscape created by WP4 partners during the testing phase are made available to the eDNA community through public repositories.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EV ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise(s)
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Finnish Environmental Institute
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
WP	Work Package
WUR	Wageningen University

1. Introduction

The future digital landscape proposed by eDNAqua-Plan WP3 provides a conceptual framework to make aquatic (e)DNA datasets Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). This landscape follows the typical workflow that produces eDNA datasets: samples are collected in the field (step 1) and processed in the lab (step 2). The resulting raw sequences are made available in sequence data repositories (step 3), and are bioinformatically processed to obtain ASVs/OTUs (step 4), which are then taxonomically assigned by comparing to reference databases (step 5). The resulting list of taxa occurring in the different sample locations are uploaded to biodiversity portals (step 6). Ideally, the reference sequences used in step 5 are linked to Biobank records that contain the metadata of the original specimen from which the sequence was generated (step 7). The aim of eDNAqua-Plan WP4 is to evaluate the different steps with real-life use cases to ensure that the digital landscape moves beyond a conceptual design and becomes a framework that can be practically implemented by the eDNA community.

Building on this, WP4 identified seven areas within the landscape where existing use case datasets can be used to evaluate functionality, clarify uncertainties, and identify where simplification or other improvements are needed. To this end, the use cases tested existing platforms and repositories that allow users to find and share eDNA data with the community. While doing so, effort was made to build on and learn from international “omics” initiatives outside Europe (such as BeBOP-OBON and FAIRe). FAIRe (Takahashi et al. 2025) and BeBOP (Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices, a UN Ocean Decade project, Samuel et al. 2021) are important pioneering projects that advance metadata standardization, quality control and FAIR data principles specifically dedicated to eDNA practices. They offer structured guidance and checklists, helping users adopt good practices for metadata sharing for the different workflow steps highlighted in the digital landscape. WP4 considers the FAIRe checklist as state of the art for eDNA datasets as it integrates the different existing metadata checklists /standards for DNA sequence data (GSC MIxS, TDWG DwC) and extends these with eDNA-specific terminology and workflow steps.

Based on the performed tests, the focus of this WP4 report is on 1) developing effective DMPs for aquatic eDNA studies, 2) streamlining the submission of sequence data, in particular to ENA as European INSDC repository, 3) enhancing interoperability across different data components of eDNA projects, 4) making laboratory protocols FAIR, 5) ensuring reproducibility in bioinformatic workflows, 6/ facilitating data uploads to global biodiversity portals and 7) guaranteeing reliable taxonomic assignment in eDNA studies. For each of these key areas, we describe the scope of the specific tests, the key strengths and challenges encountered during testing and recommendations for improvement. As such, the tests performed by the use cases allow to identify effective components of the digital landscape and to highlight barriers for end-users. We end the report with practical solutions suggested by the WP4 use cases.

2. Test results

A. Building Effective DMPs for Aquatic eDNA projects

A Data Management Plan (DMP) sets out how research data will be managed during and after a project. It ensures data are high-quality, secure, sustainable, and, where possible, accessible and reusable. Early planning helps avoid problems, reduces long-term effort, and clarifies the resources and costs required. As a result, many funding bodies and research institutes now require a DMP as part of grant proposals and project execution. For eDNA projects, a DMP is particularly important to ensure that complex datasets, metadata, and standards are managed consistently and remain useful for the wider research community.

1. Scope of testing

Several online DMP platforms are available (Data Stewardship Wizard, DAMAP, RDMO, DMPonline.be, DMPTool, GFBio DMP service) that contain the most important questions to be asked when starting with data management planning. These platforms provide templates tailored to specific funding calls which are structured around predefined sections covering project information and the documentation of research data, metadata, data storage and backup, data preservation after project completion, and data sharing and reuse. For the test, [DMPonline.be](https://dmponline.be) was used to create a DMP for a marine use case, and DMPTool and GFBio DMP service for a freshwater use case. The first two platforms co-develop and maintain a single open-source platform for DMPs: DMPRoadmap. The source code has been made available under an MIT License to permit others to reuse the code freely.

2. Key strengths

Access to these tools was found to be straightforward. The tools provide clear structures and easy options for updating and sharing the DMP.

3. Identified challenges

All platforms relied on generic templates that are not tailored to genome or eDNA data. This makes it hard to know which information should be provided and which checklists are available to standardise eDNA datasets. The lack of clear guidance leaves considerable room for interpretation, making it time-consuming to produce a well-structured and consistent DMP for eDNA projects. For less experienced people there is a risk that relevant information on data handling and storage are missed.

4. Recommendations for improvement

Improvements could be achieved by providing an omics specific template with a structure that reflects the eDNA data workflow of the digital landscape. The template should contain a list of the different datasets and datatypes typical for eDNA projects. Integrating recognised metadata standards (e.g., FAIRe, MixS, MIMARKS, DwC) would raise researchers' awareness of applicable standards, reduce the time required to complete the template, promote greater harmonisation in eDNA data reporting and ensure compliance with FAIR principles.

B. Simplifying the Path for Efficient eDNA Sequence Data Submission to ENA

As the amount and size of sequence datasets steadily increases, so does the demand for efficient deposition of sequence data in suitable repositories, and following FAIR principles. The INSDC European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and NCBI's Sequence Read Archive (SRA) are the most widely used repositories for raw sequence data submission. Previous WP4 work highlighted that the use cases only seldom submit their datasets to the European Nucleotide Archive repository.

1. Scope of testing

Freshwater (SYKE, UDE, INRAE) and marine (WUR, UMinho) datasets were uploaded to ENA, including data from different environments and genetic markers, and accordingly using different ENA checklists. In preparation of this exercise, a "Simplified ENA upload guideline" was distilled from the extensive "General Guide On ENA Data Submission". The simplified version was used as a basis for ENA sequence uploads by some of the WP4 use cases.

2. Key strengths

A key strength of ENA is the relatively easy upload procedure once the structure of ENA and the order of uploading the different kinds of data (study => sample => experiment/run => registering and uploading read data) are understood. Several users indicated that the "simplified guideline" aided in uploading data. Further, the interface (Webin Portal) was highlighted as user-friendly and easy-to-use.

3. Identified challenges

The upload to ENA was not intuitive and too challenging without condensed information on how to do so or reading most of the existing guideline. Even use case experts failed in the upload. The provided "simplified guideline" can help in overcoming the initial hurdle, but should be further improved and tailored to different data from different environments requiring different ENA checklists. Further challenges were errors with invalid file checksums, interrupted sample downloads and the need of manual resumption, lack of integration of FAIRe metadata, and errors with tax_ID.

4. Recommendations for improvement

In order to cater to the increasing number and size of datasets produced on the one side and the implementation of FAIRe and other metadata standards on the other side, it will be crucial to maximise automatism of uploading sequence data and accompanying metadata. Self-made scripts for creating and uploading files already exist (WUR) or are under development (UDE). These scripts should ideally ensure that the resulting files for upload include all FAIRe metadata fields. Also generating an official "short instructions" is recommended, as it will decrease the initial hurdle of uploading data to ENA for many users. Also, brokerage services exist to support upload (e.g., in Germany GFBIO) but those are largely unknown. A FAQ section that lists specific errors and error messages, explains how to transform/convert files into the format used by ENA, and containing example files for the different datatypes would greatly enhance the user-friendliness of the ENA platform for the eDNA community.

C. Towards Interoperability Between the Various Data Components of eDNA Projects

eDNA projects comprise multiple components, including project metadata, sample information, experiment runs, raw sequences, cleaned and raw ASV/OTU data (for metabarcoding studies), and taxonomic assignments. To ensure interoperability and efficient submission to digital repositories, it is essential to adopt a uniform vocabulary across datasets and studies. At this moment, the FAIR checklist v1.0.2 of the FAIR eDNA project is most advanced for eDNA datasets and provides term names for 338 parameters linked to the various aspects of an eDNA project using metabarcoding or species-specific qPCR assays. There is a template generator available that structures the parameters into different sheets in an excel following the eDNA workflow. Ideally, completing a template should allow users to extract the necessary data for upload to the various repositories within the digital landscape (the one stop shop mentioned by WP3).

1. Scope of testing

Several tests were conducted to evaluate the application of the FAIR checklist and templates for aquatic eDNA datasets. The FAIR v1.02 metadata template was assessed for ease of use and compliance for upload to sequence and biodiversity repositories using three marine (EV ILVO, UMinho, UNESCO) and two freshwater (UDE, BIOPOLIS) use cases. The FAIR-ator R script which generates project specific FAIR metadata templates and the FAIR-fier web tool which checks whether the metadata file is correctly filled in were tested for user-friendliness. The FAIR checklist (v1.0.3) was applied to a freshwater mitogenomic dataset to evaluate to what extent the FAIR template can be used for non-marker based eDNA surveys.

2. Key strengths

The FAIR metadata template significantly improves metadata registration compared to the MIMARKS templates. The latter contain many fields linked to physical and chemical properties of the water and sediment which are seldom measured in eDNA studies. In contrast, the FAIR template collects detailed environmental and methodological metadata tailored to eDNA studies such as filtration volume, preservation method, positive controls, blanks, etc, which are not covered in BioProjects/BioSamples. The FAIR metadata fields are clearly structured according to the eDNA workflow, which makes metadata entry intuitive. A good description and example input values are available for each field which facilitates standardisation. FAIR emphasizes the use of ontologies, while BioProjects/BioSamples allow more free text, leading to less standardization. FAIR is also designed to support interoperability with biodiversity databases like OBIS and GBIF. The template can be used as a checklist to ensure metadata completeness and to standardize reporting across projects and users.

The FAIR-ator R script that creates the metadata template is very easy to use and generates specific templates based on five user defined parameters. Depending on these parameters, the number of terms are tailored to the really needed ones for the study at hand (e.g. metabarcoding or qPCR datasets, water or sediment eDNA). The FAIR-fier webtool is easy to use and very practical to ensure the terms in the metadata template are correctly filled in. If mandatory fields are missing or the correct syntax for parameters is not used, a warning is transmitted to the user.

3. Identified challenges

During testing, it became clear that there is a misalignment between the FAIRe metadata field names and the existing ENA/SRA templates. Consequently, direct submission to ENA/SRA from the FAIRe template is not yet possible without additional adjustments. In terms of usability, the field descriptions, example data and field type information are provided as comments, which is suboptimal as it prevents simultaneous viewing and editing of metadata. The FAIRe template also contains sheets to list the taxonomy of ASV/OTU. However, excel is constrained by row and column limits which may be problematic for large eDNA metabarcoding studies. Finally, the scope of terms is heavily oriented towards PCR-based approaches (metabarcoding or qPCR). Many fields in the experiment- and taxa-related category are not applicable to shotgun sequencing methods, limiting the template's applicability for other eDNA workflows.

4. Recommendations for improvement

The FAIRe template is an important step forward to lower the hurdle of data submission to various repositories but currently functions more as a pre-submission harmonization tool rather than a direct submission template. Further improvement in usability and clarity can be achieved by ensuring that explanations for the metadata fields are listed in a separate column rather than via the comment function. Alignment between field names is needed to ensure that the data from this template can be directly used for uploading data to various repositories (ENA, NCBI, GBIF, OBIS). The availability of conversion scripts that make this alignment happen would be a big improvement for the eDNA community. The addition of metadata fields describing the metagenomic workflow to the FAIRe template is needed so that all eDNA datasets can benefit from this template.

D. Making eDNA Lab Protocols FAIR and machine-readable

Laboratory protocols for generating eDNA metabarcoding datasets are typically described in the materials and methods sections of scientific publications. These descriptions often lack a clear step-by-step procedure and standardised vocabulary. Consequently, harmonization and the exchange of omics protocols is challenging (Samuel et al. 2021). Platforms such as protocols.io promote detailed step-by-step protocols, but the use of such platforms is not yet widely adopted in the eDNA community. The inclusion of standardized metadata tags with a defined syntax (terminology) and categories such as the Minimum Information for an Omic Protocol (MIOP) and the FAIRe terms ensure that protocols can be indexed, filtered, and searched automatically (e.g., by keywords, methods, reagents). The BeBOP-OBON project provides structured protocol templates for various steps in the eDNA workflow and a step-by-step guide on how to make the protocols available through github repositories. Ideally, lab protocols should be made machine-readable to further improve automatisisation, quality control, reproducibility and re-usability of the laboratory procedure.

1. Scope of testing

The use cases tested how easy it was to transform their protocols to the BEBOP templates, including the addition of standardised metadata tags as proposed by MIOP and FAIRe. For this test, protocols for generating metabarcoding (EV ILVO, UNESCO), metagenome (UVEG), mitogenome (BIOPOLIS) and whole genome (WUR) datasets were used. The protocols.io was also evaluated for metabarcoding datasets (UDE).

Protocols were either manually converted (EV ILVO, UNESCO, BIOPOLIS), or with the help of ChatGPT (WUR and UVEG).

2. Key strengths

Several strong points of the BeBOP protocols were identified. The protocol templates are highly detailed and well-structured and all relevant information can be documented in an organized way. The inclusion of standardized MIOP and FAIRe terms allows easy searching and comparison of protocols across different studies. In addition, the explanation on how to make the protocols public through Github is clear, and this system supports version control and allows logical linking between protocols, for example when one protocol needs to be executed before or after another. The use of standardized tables and uniform steps ensures consistency and naturally guides users through the process of collecting metadata – even for aspects that might otherwise be overlooked.

An existing Word document could be converted within seconds into Markdown format using the available BeBOP templates and ChatGPT. This saved considerable manual effort and significantly accelerated the process, while also highlighting missing key details in the original protocol, such as software versions or reagent catalogue numbers.

For the protocols.io platform, the visual interface is seen as an advantage, as protocols and required reagents can be listed and displayed in a clear and accessible way.

3. Identified challenges

The use of Markdown to create the protocols posed challenges for staff unfamiliar with programming. The absence of a “track changes” function complicated collaboration (e.g. between the scientists and the lab technicians), as managing pull requests and merging edits required experience with Github. However, this is not insurmountable, and once familiar with the Markdown format and github, protocol conversion was easily done.

AI-assisted conversion was considered useful for initial formatting, but the AI-generated protocol contained inaccuracies such as incorrect reagent volumes, omitted steps, and fabricated details. This necessitated thorough human review, reducing potential time savings. The process of releasing protocol versions in Github and linking them to a DOI remained unclear as none of the use cases executed this step.

The biggest challenge and frustration for all use cases was finding the correct terms (“syntax”) for the MIOP and FAIRe metadata sections: this was difficult due to dead or scattered links to checklists like OBI, ENVO and GAZ and due to unclarity on how to find the correct terms from these checklists for the study at hand. In addition, the FAIRe terms treat different marker genes as separate protocols, whereas in practice multiple assays can be combined in one protocol, creating inconsistencies between the metadata yaml section and the SOP of the protocol. The BeBOP template for metagenomics is very basic and largely based on the metabarcoding workflow. This caused uncertainty in structuring specific steps, and adding the correct MIOP and FAIRe metadata tags was difficult as both are centred around PCR-based data generation.

The protocols.io platform is now Springer Nature-owned, which raises concern about long-term accessibility if moved behind paywalls.

Finally, there appears to be confusion about making protocols FAIR and making them machine-readable. Several WP4 use cases as well as the BEBOP github page

assumed that adding the metadata tags to the protocol made them machine-readable. However, the protocols are machine-readable when they comprise a structured representation of the procedural steps containing defined fields with strict syntax such as what action was performed, input, output, duration, parameters, software, temperature.

4. Recommendations for improvement

Overall, all use cases were positive about the BeBOP protocols and github platform as a powerful tool for documenting protocols in an efficient, standardized, and well-organized manner. Recommendations focus on making the links to the metadata standards (OBI, GAZ, ENVO) more clear in the BEBOP repository: if terms and controlled vocabulary could be searchable from a unique point/site the creation of FAIR protocols would be easier. Also, if standard terminology is agreed upon, WP4 recommends that there is a continuous training of users on how to use this, for example through webinars or a tutorial. The use cases also identified the need for an additional protocol template for metagenomic workflows.

Adding standardised metadata terms ensures that a protocol meets FAIR principles at the document level (i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable), but does not yet allow machine actions at the level of lab execution. Such machine-readable protocols would further improve reproducibility and re-usability of workflows across labs, institutes and studies.

E. Ensuring Reproducibility in eDNA Bioinformatic Workflows

One of the biggest challenges in the eDNA workflow is making the bioinformatic pipeline that turns raw sequencing data into species lists FAIR, because there are numerous options and pipelines to choose from. This information is generally outlined in scientific publications and the code used to process the data is added to repositories such as Zenodo or Github. However, this approach does not allow integration of the bioinformatic metadata into a searchable format. The FAIR checklist contains 38 fields to describe the bioinformatics process in the metadata of the project. None of these fields are mandatory, which allows the user to skip this information.

1. Scope of testing

WP4 use cases with metabarcoding (UNESCO) and metagenomics data (UVEG) tested how well the FAIR terms describe their bioinformatic processing and the critical parameter decisions in their analysis workflow.

2. Key strengths

The FAIR terms covered all major steps of the metabarcoding bioinformatics workflow. For the initial steps of data processing that are common to both metabarcoding and metagenomics, the FAIR terms are clear and very useful. This is mainly in relation to initial quality control, adapter and primer removal, and read merging. There are also several relevant FAIR terms prioritising reproducible bioinformatic analyses, such as “sop_bioinformatics” and “code_repo”, which provide a direct link to the protocols and scripts used for quality filtering, assembly or annotation and to the public repository where the analysed code is archived, respectively. With respect to taxonomic annotation, the “tax_assign_cat” is considered highly relevant because it provides information on the methodology used for taxonomic assignment of ASVs/OTUs (alignment based, nucleotide composition based, etc). In addition, the fields

“tax_id_cutoff” and “tax_query_cutoff” are very useful in evaluating the confidence of the classification. The addition of fields that describe how the raw dataset was screened for contaminants, species distribution and non-target taxa enable an understanding of what was removed from the dataset in an easy way. Finally, the “Read_counts” parameter is relevant to obtain information on how deep the sample was sequenced.

3. Identified challenges

With respect to the metabarcoding workflow, the metadata fields for taxonomic annotation are strongly focused using BLAST as an assignment tool. Consequently, the terms that are collected for the taxonomic annotation do not fit the sequence composition type of classification: the tax_id_cutoff description talks about percentage identity, which is not the same as the probability threshold used in RDP. An extra field for “tax_class_prob_threshold” is needed to accommodate this. For the reference database, there is a metadata field available to indicate whether a custom reference database was used, but there should also be a field that asks for a link to the custom reference database so that it is possible to check which species and sequences were included in the reference database.

While there are fields for the read counts of ASVs/OTUs in the DNA-derived data extension of Darwin Core (organismQuantity, organismQuantityType, sampleSizeValue and sampleSizeUnit), these are lacking in the current FAIRe checklist version. It is important to make sure that read counts are sufficiently recorded and available for each sequence and for the sample total (to enable calculation of relative abundance).

The usefulness of the FAIRe terms decreases dramatically once the workflow deviates from the ASV/OTU-centric approach. Crucial steps in a metagenomic pipeline that are not covered by FAIRe include de novo assembly of reads to reconstruct contigs and scaffolds, gene prediction and functional annotation, the process of grouping contigs into draft genomes (MAGs), quality control and refinement of MAGs and taxonomic classification of MAGs using phylogenomic approaches. The total absence of terms to document the databases used for functional annotation (KEGG, COG, Pfam), the assembly software, the critical assembly parameters, the binning algorithms or the quality of the reconstructed genomes is problematic. Finally, the result of a metagenomic pipeline is not a simple table of ASVs/OTUs, but a much more complex dataset: a catalogue of non-redundant genes, a set of MAGs with their respective taxonomic and functional annotations, etc. The FAIRe structure has no place to store this information.

4. Recommendations for improvement

Additional metadata fields that cover non-alignment based assignment tools are needed to fully make the bioinformatics workflow of eDNA studies FAIR.

A ‘FAIRe-Metagenomics’ extension module with a checklist specifically for metagenomics eDNA-derived data including terms from the MIMS (Minimum Information for a Metagenomic Sequence, Kottman et al. 2008) and MIMAG (Minimum Information for a Metagenomic Assembled Genome, Bowers et al. 2017) checklists of the Genome Standards Consortium (GSC) is needed. This extension module should also include the description of different types of result files beyond the occurrence table, such as gene catalogues or MAG coverage tables and should promote integration with specialised repositories such as metagenome analysis platforms, where functional data and MAGs can be explored interactively.

F. Facilitating eDNA Data Uploads to Global Repositories

The deposition of processed sequence reads (ASVs, OTUs) and DNA-based species occurrence data is far from common practice in the eDNA community. GBIF has recently published the Metabarcoding Toolkit (MDT) to facilitate such upload, and dataflow from GBIF publishers to OBIS is possible by simply checking the specific checkbox for sharing with a network. There is a very well documented user guide available (GBIF secretariat, 2024) as well as a simple quick start guide on how the data should look like and on how to upload the data. In addition, the FAIR eDNA project has provided the FAIRe2MDT R script to convert FAIR eDNA data templates for GBIF submission via the MDT.

1. Scope of testing

Four metabarcoding use cases (EV ILVO, WUR, BIOPOLIS and SYKE) tested the MDT toolbox from GBIF and/or the FAIReMDT conversion script. Although GBIF's MDT is not yet fully adapted to the complexity of metagenomic data, a metagenomic datasets (UVEG) was used to format and upload a set of species occurrence data to GBIF to evaluate the suitability and limitations of MDT and FAIRe metadata templates for data that do not come from a PCR-based method. The taxonomic occurrence data was obtained by assigning metagenomic reads to the 16S and 18S marker genes. The MDT Sandbox installation was also used to test the submission of long read Nanopore metabarcoding data (WUR).

2. Key strengths

GBIF has a very well documented user manual and a step by step guide with instructions and example data to upload metabarcoding based species occurrence data. Even for first time users, it is very clear on how the input data file should look like. This input file consists of an excel with four sheets (OTU/ASV table, taxonomy, sample info and study specific info). If raw sequence data have already been submitted to SRA, then many of the fields can be easily copied from the MIMARKS file. In addition, the FAIRe2MDT conversion script takes the relevant information from the FAIRe template file to create the GBIF input file.

The MDT allows an easy conversion of the excel input file to DwC format and has a straightforward way to publish the dataset on the GBIF portal.

The simplified data flow from GBIF to OBIS via a simple checkbox is very efficient.

3. Identified challenges

The GBIF template allows linking to URLs of raw sequence data (field associatedSequences) and of the biosamples that have been submitted to SRA or ENA (materialSampleID). Getting these URLs from SRA is not straightforward.

Species occurrence data is centered towards metabarcoding data. This implies a loss of information and a devaluation of the sequencing effort for metagenomic datasets. In addition, the current GBIF template lacks fields for key metadata to describe critical parameters of metagenomic analysis, such as assembly methods, MAG binning, or genomic reference databases used in metagenomics.

Data can only be published through institutional access to the GBIF publishing portal. In addition, users need to be linked to the institutional account, which can only be done by contacting the national contact points. For Belgium, this was a very easy process, in Portugal contact was established through this WP4 exercise.

4. Recommendations for improvement

A simple guide with instructions on how to obtain the URLs of raw sequencing data from nucleotide repositories would make it easier to provide the links with the raw sequencing data.

Data submitted to GBIF can be easily transferred to OBIS, by associating a network at the publishing step. This step can however easily be forgotten, and a more evident OBIS specific checkbox is recommended. Although work is already underway, it would be very useful to accelerate the development of Darwin Core extensions for metagenomic data. This would involve creating a specific guide or 'Metagenomic Toolkit' for GBIF/OBIS that covers the publication of different data 'layers': the taxonomic layer (occurrences), the functional layer and the MAG layer, and ideally linking this to whole genome repositories so that metagenome taxonomic assignments can be traceable and verifiable.

G. Towards Reliable Taxonomic Assignment of eDNA sequence data

A crucial step in DNA-based studies is linking the DNA sequence data to a taxonomic name. WP3 identified three levels of available reference databases: broad range nucleotide databases, quality controlled databases and taxonomically curated, specialised databases. WP4 already highlighted that specialised in-house reference databases tailored to the geographic region or taxa of interest often do not meet the FAIR criteria as they lack information on how the reference sequences were selected (e.g., how was the species list from the area obtained, from where were the DNA sequences retrieved, how was the taxonomic identification verified). T3.1 provided a list of minimum requirements to which a reference sequence should comply to obtain the most reliable link between taxonomic identification of the specimen and its DNA sequence.

1. Scope of testing

Project partners outlined the procedure of assigning taxonomy to the sequences of their test cases and evaluated the minimum metadata requirements proposed by T3.1 for reference sequences with respect to the relevance of their specific eDNA dataset (short read metabarcoding: UDE; long read metabarcoding: WUR; mitogenomics: BIOPOLIS and metagenomics: UVEG) to ensure the requirements proposed by T3.1 are fit for purpose and applicable to all types of eDNA datasets.

2. Key strengths

There is common agreement on the requirement of certain metadata (e.g., taxonomic name following the international nomenclature rules, unique sample ID, name of identifier, genetic marker and used primers) for reference sequences. When sequences are accompanied with all the metadata, high quality reference databases can be created by retrieving reference sequences based on specific search criteria. In addition, when different taxonomic names are linked to the same DNA sequence, the accompanying metadata fields can help in deciding which taxonomic name is most likely (e.g., if one species does not occur in the area of collection and the other species does, it is highly likely to be the latter species; or if the voucher specimen of species 1 has clear diagnostic features while the voucher specimen of species 2 not, then it is more likely that the taxonomy of the first species is correct).

3. Identified challenges

Some of the suggested obligatory metadata are not always applicable (e.g., "reference of the document": not all reference sequences are published outside reference

databases; “confidence level of taxonomic assignment”: who decides that and if the concept is based on self-assessment, how do you assess e.g. museum material). High resolution images of diagnostic features require substantial effort and taxonomic expertise which hampers large scale production of reference sequences. However, this morphological information is an essential back-up to validate the morphology in the future. The two use cases with metagenomic datasets (WUR and BIOPOLIS) highlighted that the DNA marker metadata criteria (section 4.6 in the checklist of T3.1) are not applicable for their reference databases. Since these are obligatory, metagenomic reference sequence data can not meet the criteria as currently proposed by T3.1. The checklist does not include fields that describe the sequencing technology or the method used to obtain the consensus sequence while such metadata allows to interpret the quality of the sequence.

By far the biggest challenge is that having reference sequences with most or all obligatory and recommended metadata does not automatically translate into a correct taxonomic assignment of sequences from metabarcoding or metagenomic studies. Public databases such as BOLD or Genbank contain millions of reference sequences covering a gradient in quality and taxonomic correctness. This includes reference sequences with all mandatory metadata, as defined here, that are incorrect taxonomic references merely due to incorrect morphological identification of the respective voucher specimen. In case of reverse BIN taxonomy, as practiced by BOLD, evaluating the quality of reference sequences based on their metadata might be flawed, as the taxonomic id of a sequence in that case is not an original attribute to that sequence, but attributed secondarily by using the taxonomic information of other sequences of the same BIN.

On a practical level, every single metabarcoding dataset contains thousands of OTUs or even more ASVs that need to be taxonomically assigned. While most scientists will consider the “sequence similarity” of a reference sequence for retaining or discarding a species name (or other taxonomic level), all the other metadata are mostly neglected in evaluating the robustness of a taxonomic assignment. It is unfeasible to manually evaluate the robustness of taxonomic assignments for every single OTU/ASV, even more so in the future when the amount and size of datasets will continue to grow.

4. Recommendations for improvement

The checklist of metadata accompanying reference sequences would benefit from the inclusion of fields that provide information on the sequencing technology used (e.g. long-read or short-read) and on the bioinformatic procedure used to obtain the consensus sequences (e.g. which basecalling software was used and what filtering criteria?), while this information is relevant for interpreting the quality of the sequence in the database.

The solution to routinely obtaining robust taxonomic assignments of eDNA sequence data lays in critical evaluation of results at two different levels: 1) curation of reference sequences in databases by expert taxonomists and 2) availability of robust bioinformatic pipelines that create reliable reference databases from publically available reference repositories. The Meta-Fish-Lib pipeline (Collins et al. 2021) and the SeqRanker pipeline (under development, <https://github.com/TillMacher/dbDNA>) are excellent examples of this. Such scripts allow retrieval of all sequences from a set of species from a species list, and for various barcode marker genes. Subsequent phylogenetic screening allows flagging potential problematic sequences (for example, identical sequences with different taxonomic names). Species with only a single reference sequence are also listed, so that manual curation can be done. For instance, if this sequence is phylogenetically placed near congeneric sequences but sufficiently

different, the taxonomic name is very likely to be correct. If it is placed within sequences of a congeneric species, this may point to a wrong taxonomic identification and the user can decide to remove the sequence from the reference database. Taxonomic assignment of taxa with low resolution in the marker gene at study can and should also be flagged, e.g. by screening BLASTn hits for percentage identity. Curation of reference databases allows even non-expert users to assign taxonomy, but comes at the cost of losing relevant sequence data that has not been curated yet. Combining the two levels of evaluation allows experienced users to take advantage of as much sequence data as possible at any time. The digital landscape of the future should be built in such a way that both experienced and non-professional users can obtain reliable taxonomic IDs.

Obtaining high resolution digital images of diagnostic traits of the specimen from which the reference sequence was generated is time consuming and only possible by expert taxonomists, but this can never be a reason to settle for less. Instead, the digital vouchers are highly valuable and showcase the exceptional knowledge embedded in taxonomy. In addition, these high quality images can be used as training material for the next generation of taxonomists.

Lastly, sequences taxonomically annotated by reverse BIN taxonomy should never be used as a taxonomic reference, but can be used as a geographic reference.

3. Practical solutions to increase the operational aspect of the digital landscape

Moving towards FAIR eDNA datasets from sampling through laboratory processing, and from bioinformatic analysis to publishing requires adaptations at various steps in the eDNA workflow to facilitate the uptake of the FAIR principles by data producers. The use cases found that a number of very simple steps might already have big effects in making the digital landscape fit for purpose. The following six materials were created by the WP4 partners during testing and will be made available to the eDNA community through the eDNAqua-Plan website and dedicated websites:

- 1) DMP templates that are tailored towards eDNA projects and that directly follow the digital landscape structure will guide users on which datasets can be generated, which file naming should be used, where and how the data should be handled, including information on checklists to be used for documentation and for improved FAIRness of the datasets. A template for eDNA projects will be developed by M30 (February 2026) and made available in DMPonline. (lead EV ILVO, UDE)
- 2) The BeBOP project welcomes contributions of new types of templates to their collection. The use cases with meta- and mitogenomic datasets tested the BeBOP template and found the template too PCR oriented. Their metagenomic protocols will be used to create a metagenomics template which will be provided to the BeBOP github page by M30 (February 2026). (lead UVEG, BIOPOLIS, WUR)
- 3) When uploading species occurrence data to the github repository, the URLs of the raw sequencing data from SRA/ENA can be added. There is now a dedicated github repository available from EV ILVO that outlines how to create the input file for GBIF if you have ASV data that need to be linked to SRA biosample data with MIMARKS ([DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17209409](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17209409)). The script has also been communicated to the GBIF secretariat, who is actively looking to incorporate this into the GBIF manual.
- 4) Simplifying the submission of eDNA raw sequence data and the accompanying sample metadata will be operationalised through a collaboration with ENA experts in eDNAqua-

Plan and the WP4 partners UDE and WUR. Specifically, a simplified guide and example scripts for data submission will be made available by M30 (February 2026) through Zenodo with special attention for uptake of FAIR terms in the metadata fields by ENA (lead UDE, WUR)

- 5) The use of AI to generate laboratory protocols in Markdown format proved to be very time efficient. A manual on how to convert laboratory protocols into the BeBOP markdown based protocols using ChatGPT will be made available on Zenodo by M30 (February 2026) (lead WUR, UVEG)
- 6) A guideline on what the key aspects are for reliable reference sequences and for robust taxonomic assignment of eDNA datasets is currently being written in two scientific papers by WP2 and WP3, in collaboration with some WP4 partners (UDE, INRAE, UMinho). Publication of these papers is scheduled before the end of the eDNAqua-Plan project (August 2028).

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